

Criteria for a good scientific presentation

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Topic

The publication '**Criteria for a good scientific presentation**' provides practical advice for preparing a presentation of scientific results, for example at a scientific congress or a conference. The aim of a scientific presentation is to enter into a scientific discourse and professional exchange with the audience.

The article is part of a more comprehensive article on 'Good scientific presentation', which consists of three parts: 1-Criteria for a good scientific presentation (this article), 2-checklist, 3-tips and tricks.

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Foreword

Scientists want and need to present their results. In this context, "scientific presentation" refers to a scientific lecture that conveys information and results that are reproduced on slides, for example. It is about the presentation of scientific results, for example at a scientific congress, such as the Rehabilitation Science Colloquium. The aim of a scientific presentation is to enter into a scientific discourse and professional exchange with the audience. The article do not addresses other aspects of a scientific presentation, such as rhetoric during the lecture or design elements of the slides.

The complete publication 'Good scientific presentation: Criteria, Checklist, Tips and Tricks' consists of a main article (this article) and two further individual articles. All three articles contain different aspects and are each published separately:

1. **Criteria for a good scientific presentation:** <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064590>
2. **Evaluation of a scientific presentation using a checklist:**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064504>
3. **Tips and tricks for creating and giving a scientific presentation:**
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064725>

1	The Criteria for a good scientific presentation apply primarily to empirical studies, but can also be used for reviews and meta-analyses as well as qualitative studies.
2	The checklist wants to help lecturers ensure a high quality of scientific presentations. Presenters are required to check their presentation for these criteria and to adhere to the prescribed structure for scientific presentations. This can be achieved and checked with the help of the checklist. You can use the checklist to have a (trial) presentation evaluated, for example in your own team or circle of colleagues.
3	The tips and tricks provide practical advice on designing slides and giving a confident holding of a presentation in front of a specialist audience.

This publication was created at the suggestion and in exchange with the members of the 'Working Group: Methods' in the German Society for Rehabilitation Sciences (DGRW, <https://www.dgrw-online.de>).

1. Criteria for a good scientific presentation

Scientists attach great importance to the detailed planning, accurate execution and conscientious evaluation of a study. Available results should be published in a suitable form. Depending on the type of the study, there are already various requirements and reporting guidelines for writing a publication. Perhaps the best known are the CONSORT statements for randomized trials (Moher et al 2001, Schulz et al 2010), the STROBE statements for observational studies (von Elm et al 2007), the COREQ checklist for qualitative interview studies and focus groups (Tong et al 2007), and the PRISMA statements for systematic reviews (Page et al 2021). For almost every type of study, there are a large number of guidelines for written reporting, some of which also include a checklist for querying relevant aspects (EQUATOR Network 2022). For the oral presentation of the study results in the form of a lecture, there is - to the best of the authors' knowledge - no corresponding counterpart so far. The article by Foster et al provides good practice recommendations for abstracts and presentations in a scientific-medical context (Good Practice for Conference Abstracts and Presentations: GPCAP), although this focus more on formalities (Foster et al 2019).

The aim of this article is to present important criteria for a good scientific presentation. A distinction is made between structural and content-related aspects. A scientific presentation has a certain formal structure with individual sections (see chapter 'Structure'). For an accurate description of the presented studie(s), there are also content-related criteria. Content-related aspects of the studie(s) are listed in the 'Material/Population/Methods/Statistics' section of the chapter 'Structure'. The content criteria for a good scientific presentation apply primarily to empirical studies, but can also be used for meta-analyses, reviews and qualitative studies. The more general approach should help presenters to achieve a high quality of their medical/scientific presentation. High-quality presentations increase the benefit for listeners and thus the usability of the study results. For a good presentation, it is important to keep the interests and intentions of the audience in mind. Think about your audience in advance, i.e. your target group: such as a specialist audience, colleagues or laypeople. This is important in order to decide what knowledge can be assumed and what information may still need to be provided.

This article is intended to support experienced and less experienced speakers in preparing a scientifically good presentation and presenting their results adequately, as well as the related publications *'Evaluation of a scientific presentation using a checklist'* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064504>) and *'Tips and tricks for creating and giving a scientific presentation'* (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15064725>).

The proposals for a high-quality presentation are based on the authors' many years of practical experience and extensive literature research. The two series 'Evaluation of Scientific Publications' (Deutsches Ärzteblatt International) and 'Methods in Rehabilitation Research' (Die Rehabilitation) as well as suitable textbooks and publications on the planning and design of medical studies (Döring and Bortz 2016, Weiß 2019, Wirtz 2020) provide the content recommendations for this article. The intensive discussions and the lively exchange with the members of the 'Working Group: Methods' of the German Society for Rehabilitation Sciences (DGRW) should be emphasized, which contributed significantly to the success of the project.

Preparation

Listeners: Who are the people to whom you are transmitting the information? For example, researchers, physicians, practitioners, politicians, citizens or a mixed audience. Depending on the target audience, different knowledge and interests can be assumed, which must be taken into account in the presentation. For example, the interests and backgrounds of clinicians, established doctors, therapists and members of a working group or team in a hospital differ from a larger, more scientifically oriented audience. The aim of a scientific presentation is to enter into a scientific discourse and professional exchange with the audience.

Core message: What is the core message or core messages of your presentation (Take Home Message)? What should the audience (absolutely!) take away from your presentation? Think about this in the first step, this will make it easier for you to focus on the essentials of the presentation and serve as a 'red line' when giving your presentation.

Structure

This chapter provides information on the formal organization and structure of a scientific presentation. The structure of the presentation of empirical data is essentially identical to the structure of scientific publications, like journal-articles. As a rule, there are time limits for the presentation on the part of the organizer. Consider this during preparation.

A presentation is created with a suitable presentation program and consists of these sections:

	Title slide
	Introduction
	Aim and Question
	Methods
	Presentation of results
	Discussion
	Conclusion
	Conflict of interest and research funding

Title slide

Often, the title slide (1st slide) has a different design. For example, the background is different, the font is larger and has a different color. The title slide often features the employer's logo and suitable pictograms or images embellish the first slide of the presentation.

The title slide includes the following aspects:

- Title of the presentation
- Names of the authors, including affiliation to an institution / clinic / company (affiliation)
- Reason for the lecture as well as date and place of the event

Introduction

- The introduction of a scientific presentation should be short and concise, especially if you have a tight time budget. In the introduction, you describe the current state of research and then formulate the research question. Introduction to the topic: relevance, theoretical and practical background, state of the art, literature review
- Explanation of the reasons for the study: problem outline, open questions, contradictions, ambiguities and research design

Aim and Question

The central question(s) is or are the core of your scientific presentation and serves as a common thread for you. The research question links the chapters Introduction, Methods, Presentation of Results and Discussion. Therefore, you should present the question on a separate slide.

- The research question should be formulated precisely and in detail: Only a precisely formulated question can be answered exactly and criticized accordingly
- Selection and weighting of the research question: Make clear which research question is the focus of the presentation. In clinical trials, one primary question is usually formulated that is the focus of the presentation. But even in exploratory projects, a selection of a few questions should be made - if only for reasons of time

This section is the basis for the evaluation of the subsequent presentation of the results and is therefore indispensable and important. Listener can only understand the results and conclusions if you present the method used in detail. This creates the necessary transparency. To achieve this, you must provide all the relevant information.

- Description of the population by inclusion and exclusion criteria (selection criteria)
- Description of sampling and recruitment
- Description of the study design (e.g. research question, type of evaluation, study type, control group, study with/without randomization, sample size estimation/case number planning, sample/study population, measurement method: diagnostics, assessments, number of measurement points, observation unit etc.)
- Information on the measuring instruments and variables collected
- Specification of statistical analysis methods, including criteria for assessing statistical significance: Indication of the type of evaluation - descriptive, exploratory or confirmatory - as well as indication and evaluation of the significance level Alpha
- Dealing with missing values
- If applicable, specify the evaluation software: statistical programs such as R, Stata®, SPSS®, Statistica®, SAS® or others
- Research ethics: In studies with humans or animals, an existing ethics vote or references to compliance with ethical codes (Helsinki Declaration, DFG, etc.) should be indicated: on a separate slide, possibly at the end of the presentation
- If applicable, information on study protocol and study registration

Content of a study (study design)

In addition to the prescribed formal structure of the presentation - i.e. the formal structure of the lecture - the description of a study also includes aspects of content.

The content criteria of a study are described by the term '**design of the study**' (**study design**) and can be divided into six areas (Röhrig et al, 2009a):

- 1) Research question / type of evaluation
- 2) Study type
- 3) Sample size estimation/case number planning
- 4) Observation unit
- 5) Sample/study population
- 6) Measurement method

The study design influences both the presentation of results and the interpretation of a study. Therefore, you should describe the essential aspects of the examination in a presentation.

1) Research question / type of evaluation The problem outline derive the research question	2) Study type The study type describes the type of survey and study implementation	3) Sample size estimation / case number of planning Information on sample size estimation or of case number planning
4) Observation Unit Naming of investigation Unit and Trait Carrier	5) Sample/Study population Transparent presentation of sample recruitment and description	6) Measurement method Description of the measurement method

For content-related aspects, the design and the associated quality of a study you can also use the PICO concept as an alternative to the classification into six areas ('design of the study'), (Wikipedia – The Free Encyclopedia 2024, JBI GLOBAL WIKI 2024). PICO is a method for a good description of a research question using the four terms "**P**opulation, **I**ntervention, **C**ontrol and **O**utcome".

1) Research question / type of evaluation

The problem outline leads to the research question/questions. The research question can also be described very well using the PICO scheme

- What is the exact research question of the presentation?
- Answering the seven questions: why, who, what, how, when, where and how many?
- How was the question operationalized? What variables were collected for this purpose? Why?
- Target variable(s): Indication of primary and/or secondary target variables: Which variables were collected? For what purpose?
- Type of evaluation:
 - **Descriptive:** (Pure) description of the population
 - **Exploratory:** recording and evaluation of relationships, development of hypotheses: P-values are not (!) interpreted as proof, but serve as a reference point in the sense of 'effect points in the direction' or 'presumed effect' (du Prel et al 2009), caution when making statements about causal causes
 - **Confirmatory:** Statistical evidence, statements about causal causes (e.g. in RCT studies), testing of predetermined hypotheses (ideally contained in a study protocol) with confirmation or refutation: Since the hypothesis test is interpreted as proof, type 1 and type 2 errors must be taken into account; if necessary, adjustment of p-values in several hypothesis tests, e.g. by a Bonferroni correction (du Prel et al 2009)

2) Study type (Röhrig et al 2009b)

The study type describes the type of survey and study conduct, for example prospective or retrospective, randomized survey and the presence of a control group. The type of study influences the interpretability of the results, such as causality, hypothesis generation, hypothesis testing, descriptive description, and makes statements about the quality of the study (level of evidence). The study type also implies statements on the occurrence of possible confounding variables (confounders). Therefore, you should specify the type of study and describe it precisely.

Exemplary study types

- Intervention study
 - Randomized controlled trial (RCT study, cluster RCT)
 - Controlled trial without randomization
 - Quasi-experimental study
- Observational study
 - Cohort Study
 - Case-control study
 - Therapy study
 - Cross-sectional study
 - Ecological study
 - Sample design: e.g. study with pre-post design

- Summary of studies/literature-based study (Ressing et al 2009)
 - Meta-analysis with individual data (pooled reanalysis)
 - Meta-analysis of published data
 - Systematic review
 - Simple (narrative) review
 - Scoping Review
 - Rapid Review
- Other study types
 - Health Care Study
 - Secondary data analysis
 - Qualitative study
 - Development or quality determination of assessments/technical applications/medical devices
 - Diagnostic study
 - Individual case presentation
 - Survey
 - Other study types
- Time aspect
 - Prospective study
 - Retrospective study
 - Cross-sectional study
 - Other studies
- Other aspects
 - Is there a comparison group?
 - Was the assignment randomized?
 - Blinded survey of the target variables?
 - Indication of possible distortions of the comparison group (inhomogeneities, selection bias, confounders)

3) Estimation of the number of cases/planning of the number of cases

Information on sample size estimation or sample size planning is important because the sample size influences the precision and generalization of the results as well as the size of the confidence intervals and the p-values (Kutschmann et al 2006, Röhrig et al 2010).

- Information on the estimation of the required number of observation units (e.g. patients, probands) to answer the main question (sample size estimation or planning)
- If there is knowledge of the expected effect (e.g. clinically relevant difference, minimal important difference) and its dispersion (e.g. standard deviation), the number of cases can be calculated using formulas (sample size planning). Otherwise, at least the number of cases should be estimated (sample size estimation).

4) Observation Unit

- Rehabilitation person or group/population of a region as an observation unit
- An organ, an organ system, an individual subject (animal or human), a technical model, a sub-collective as an observation unit
- In a systematic review or a meta-analysis of published data, the study or the average study results can be regarded as an observation unit
- In a meta-analysis with individual data (pooled reanalysis), the individual data serve as an observation unit

5) Sample/study population

Give the audience a good insight into the sample: who, how and when recruited. This information is important for interpreting the results and avoiding selection bias.

- Single or multicenter design: number of institutions/study centers
- Inclusion and exclusion criteria of the participants (in the case of reviews/meta-analyses: for the studies used)
- Description of the recruitment of study participants: advertisement (notice, advertisement, etc.), students/patients/persons to be treated in the department or at the hospital, register, selection of participants, etc.
- Information on the selection of the population: Random (e.g. population register) or consecutive (subsequent) selection of study participants
- Generalization from the study population to the population: information on the underlying population
- Description of the setting, examples from rehabilitation:
 - Type of rehabilitation: inpatient, outpatient or mobile; Precautionary measure
 - Indication for rehabilitation: orthopaedic, cardiological, neurological, psychosomatic or other indications
 - Facility: Clinic, outpatient center, mobile rehabilitation team
 - Medical or vocational rehabilitation (benefits for participation in working life)

6) Measurement method

- Type of measurement:
physical or chemical measurement, anthropometric data, laboratory determination, microbiological measurement, histology, questionnaire, interview, other
- Measurement instrument:
established assessment (indication of validity and reliability) vs. self-designed questionnaire
- Scale level:
characteristics can be divided into nominal, ordinal and interval-scaled scales according to their level with increasing value (simplified)
- Accuracy of measurement:
reliability and validity

- Description of the (standardized) execution of the measurement
- Objectivity:
 - possible blinding of the measurement, several raters
- Internal and external validity:
 - generalization of the results (generalizability)
- Measurement methodology:
 - number and time of measurements to be performed
- Time of the survey(s):
 - pre-post design (beginning-end), catamnesis (after completion of rehabilitation), there may be several survey times, also during therapy

Presentation of results

The statistical analysis and presentation of data is complex, this article prioritizes the naming of basic principles and important biometric measures.

In the presentation, you should concentrate on those results that are necessary to answer the central question(s). The basis is a clean descriptive presentation of the results, with indication of the actual changes or effects. Measures that are easy to understand, direct and suitable for everyday use should be preferred and abstract, theoretical, cumbersome calculable and difficult to understand measures should be avoided as far as possible.

The result of a statistical test is the p-value. P-values indicate the extent to which the result realized from the data is probable, assuming the validity of the null hypothesis H_0 (corresponds to no difference). P-values should be interpreted cautiously, as they depend not only on the size of the effect, but also on the size of the sample (number of cases) and the variance of the data (Bender and Lange 2001). P-values can be given in exploratory and confirmatory evaluation (Röhrig et al 2009a, du Prel et al 2009). The frequency and handling of missing values should be specified if necessary, for each variable and for subgroup analyses or sub-questions.

As a speaker, you should always ask yourself to what extent the results of the study are relevant for the audience. Is the content of the presentation important for everyday professional life (practice, clinic, registered doctor, service provider, research institutions)? What should the listeners take away for themselves and their patients? Depending on the audience, you may have to explain statistical values in more detail.

The following table lists important criteria for the presentation of results:

Criteria	Descriptions
Sample description	Used primarily to estimate external validity and generalizability. Can be relatively short.
Meaningful descriptive statistics	<p>Frequencies, position and scatter measures: such as mean, median, quartiles, percentiles, standard deviation, range, minimum, maximum as well as relative risks, odds ratios, hazard ratios, correlations, etc.</p> <p>If necessary, meaningful graphics can or should be used: e.g. histogram, bar chart, box-whisker plot, error bar chart, scatter plot and others (Spriestersbach et al 2008, Sachs 2003, Bortz 2005, Rougier 2014, Weissgerber et al 2015, Weissgerber et al 2017, Weissgerber et al 2019, Weiß 2019).</p>
Information on the content/clinical relevance of the results:	Effects, effectiveness of an intervention, minimal important difference (MID), achievement of clinically defined target values, etc. (Faller 2004, Höder and Hüppe 2019).
Frequency of positive or negative changes	Information on how many patients or rehabilitants benefit from the measure or improve, remain unchanged or deteriorate in a clinically relevant way (Höder and Hüppe 2019).
At least one inferential statistical measure in each case	Confidence intervals and/or p-values, especially for important target variables (du Prel et al 2009, Faller 2004). Confidence intervals indicate the confidence range of the results.
For multivariate models	Information on the overall model (e.g. R^2 for regression analyses, χ^2 test and fit indices for structural equation models) as well as information on parameters of interest in the model (regression coefficients, factor loads, etc.).
Indication of further statistical variables	Depending on the type and design of the study: effect sizes, severity groups, risks, odds ratios, hazards, incidence, prevalence, sensitivity, specificity, positive/negative predictive value, accuracy, etc.

Discussion

In the discussion, you will interpret the results and place them in the context of previous research. In doing so, pay attention to a fair and critical discussion of the results.

What is the internal and external quality of the examination? To which group of rehabilitation patients can the result be generalized (generalizability)? It is also important to describe the limitations of the study. Implications for further research, practice, therapy, clinic management/organization or policy should be derived and demonstrated. Use the following questions to structure your discussion:

<input type="checkbox"/>	Is there a close connection to the question?
<input type="checkbox"/>	How should the strength of the effects/correlations, etc. be assessed, also in comparison to other research results?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Are there any limitations with regard to the validity of the study? In particular, possible sources of error, such as confounders, selection bias, lack of randomisation and the influence of measurement methods and, if applicable, the sample size should be addressed.
<input type="checkbox"/>	What are the conclusions and consequences of the results of the study? What implications do you recommend?
<input type="checkbox"/>	For which persons/patients/rehabilitants, or which population - consisting of age, gender, sociodemographic variables, level of education, etc. - can the results of the sample be generalized? For which groups do the results not apply?
<input type="checkbox"/>	What results can practitioners/scientists or service providers or politicians use from the findings?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is the therapy, method or assessment presented suitable for the people of the target population (Röhrig et al, 2009a, figure 1)? Do the measures help those affected?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Evidence of the recommendations: Is the result or results causally explainable using causality criteria according to Bradford Hill (Hill 1965, Müller-Waldeck 2020)?
<input type="checkbox"/>	Is there a need for further research? What questions are still open?

Conclusion

The conclusion is derived from the discussion. State in one sentence - or a few sentences - what the conclusion of the presentation is.

- The most important(!) conclusions, consequences and recommendations for action
- Core message of the presentation: What should the audience take home with them, so-called take home message(s); however, do not over-interpret the results

Conflict of interest and research funding

Note on possible conflicts of interest and, if applicable, on research funding and sponsors, placed at the beginning or end of the presentation on a separate slide. You should observe the requirements of the sponsor and the congress organizer (Foster et al. 2019). In the presentation, you can list other points: Acknowledgements, authors or collaborators on the project as well as references to further information: link or QR code to the project website, supplements or other publications. You should also provide in any case information on authorship in the use of media (photos, images, graphics, audio, videos, etc.). For further information see under:

<https://support.google.com/legal/answer/3463239?hl>, <https://creativecommons.org>

We wish you every success with your presentation!

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